

Pairwise Difference Representations of Central Moments: Skewness, Kurtosis, and Higher-order Recursions

Jean-Marie Dufour¹, Abderrahim Taamouti², and Meilin Tong³

¹McGill University

²University of Liverpool

³McGill University

Abstract

We develop pairwise-difference (Gini-type) representations of higher-order central moments for both general random variables and empirical moments. These representations eliminate the need for any location parameter. For third and fourth central moments, this yields pairwise-difference representations of skewness and kurtosis coefficients. We further derive a recursion that constructs higher-order representations from lower-order components, showing that all finite central moments possess such representations without reference to the mean. This is achieved by considering i.i.d. *replications* of the random variables, by interpreting central moments as covariances between a random variable and its powers, and by establishing recursions which link the pairwise-difference representation of any moment to lower order ones. Numerical summation identities are deduced. Finally, we use these identities to derive unbiased estimators of central moments and introduce a Monte Carlo approximation estimator that remains unbiased while greatly reducing the computation cost. Simulation results comparing the proposed estimators with the usual sample-moment (“natural”) estimators demonstrate substantial bias reduction across moment orders, with the largest improvements observed at higher orders.

Key Words: Gini; Covariance; Skewness; Kurtosis; Pairwise differences.

1. Introduction and Contributions

Moments are fundamental statistical tools that summarize distributions, support comparisons across datasets, and guide assessments of model fit. In applied work, features of distributional shape, such as skewness and tail thickness, are central to areas ranging from inequality measurement to empirical finance. There is a long tradition of interpreting moments through contrasts between observations, which often yields more transparent formulas and practical estimators. For instance, Gini-type representations of variance and their extensions to covariance illustrate how dispersion and association can be viewed through pairwise differences.

The sample variance of x_1, \dots, x_n is typically defined as the average of squared deviations from the sample mean,

$$s_{\bar{X}}^2(n) := \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2, \quad \bar{x} := \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i. \quad (1.1)$$

A classical result, due to [Gini \(1912\)](#), shows that $s_{\bar{X}}^2(n)$ can be written equivalently as an average of *all* pairwise squared differences - with no explicit reference to a location parameter [see also the similar presentation in [Heffernan \(1988\)](#)].

$$s_{\bar{X}}^2(n) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n (x_i - x_j)^2 = \frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j>i}^n (x_i - x_j)^2. \quad (1.2)$$

(1.2) has two immediate interpretations that motivate the broader developments in this paper. First, the Gini representation highlights that it does not rely on the sample mean or any other location

parameter, and thus can be viewed as a measure of the *intrinsic* variability among observations. In particular, it provides a means of quantifying dispersion even when no natural location parameter exists, such as in categorical data; see [Light and Margolin \(1971\)](#) and [Margolin and Light \(1974\)](#). Second, by expressing dispersion through pairwise differences $(x_i - x_j)$, it may be easier to identify which observations exert the greatest influence on the statistic, since $(x_i - x_j)$ is local to each pair $\{i, j\}$, whereas deviations from the mean $(x_i - \bar{x})$ depend on all n observations. A comprehensive review of Gini-based statistical methods is provided by [Yitzhaki and Schechtman \(2013\)](#).

For bivariate observations $z_i = (x_i, y_i)'$, the sample covariance is

$$s_{XY}(n) := \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y}). \quad (1.3)$$

An identity due to [Hayes \(2011\)](#) yields the pairwise-difference representation

$$s_{XY}(n) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n (x_i - x_j)(y_i - y_j) = \frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j>i}^n (x_i - x_j)(y_i - y_j). \quad (1.4)$$

This form makes the interpretation immediate: $s_{XY}(n)$ measures the tendency of x and y to move in the same direction, now expressed entirely through pairwise comparisons. When both $x_i > x_j$ and $y_i > y_j$ (or both reversed), the product $(x_i - x_j)(y_i - y_j)$ is positive and contributes positively to the covariance; if the directions disagree, the contribution is negative. Moreover, because centering at (\bar{x}, \bar{y}) is not needed, (1.4) connects naturally to rank-based and alternative dependence measures that rely on orderings of pairs rather than levels; such as Kendall's and Spearman's measures of dependence [see [Lehmann \(2011\)](#)].

The idea of expressing moments via pairwise differences has been explored in multiple strands. Starting with [Gini \(1912\)](#) for variance (and expository treatments such as [Heffernan \(1988\)](#)), the approach was extended to covariance by [Hayes \(2011\)](#). Closely related expressions appear in the U -statistics literature; see [Lee \(2019, Ch. 1.\)](#). [Wright \(1992\)](#) and [Steele \(2004\)](#) relate such pairwise comparison forms to the Lagrange and Binet–Cauchy identities, which, among other things, give transparent routes to Cauchy–Schwarz-type inequalities.

Despite the clarity of (1.2) and (1.4), there has been no comparably simple and unified framework for representing *higher-order* central moments (beyond variance and covariance) in purely pairwise terms. This paper fills that gap. Motivated by the above identities, and following the storyline of our conference presentation, we refer to representations that depend only on differences between (possibly replicated) observations as *D-representations* (or “*Gini-type*” representations). Our contributions are threefold:

1. We develop a simple framework to express central moments of both general random variables and empirical moments using pairwise differences only (no location parameter).
2. We derive explicit *D-representations* for the third and fourth central moments, yielding location-free formulas for skewness and (excess) kurtosis coefficients.
3. We introduce a recursion that links higher-order *D-representations* to lower-order ones, showing that *all* finite central moments admit *D-representations*.

A key observation is that a central moment can be written as a covariance between a variable and a power of itself; coupling this with i.i.d. replications allows us to eliminate unknown locations and reduce everything to differences. These same constructions immediately produce unbiased estimators based on small kernels (and Monte Carlo averages thereof), which we evaluate against conventional “natural” estimators in simulation.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses *D-representations* for covariances and regression coefficients and shows how related numerical identities can be derived. Section 3 presents *D-representations* for the third and fourth moments, along with corresponding expressions for skewness and kurtosis coefficients. Section 4 generalizes the approach, providing recursive formula

for constructing D -representations of arbitrary moment order. Section 5 illustrates applications of the proposed representations, and Section 7 concludes. Proofs are collected in the Appendix.

2. D -representations for Covariances

Covariance describes the degree to which two random variables vary jointly. In many settings, however, one may not know, or may prefer not to carry, their means explicitly through all algebraic steps. An effective alternative is to express covariance entirely in terms of pairwise differences between independent replications. This approach removes the need for explicit centering, highlights parallel forms for variance, and naturally leads to empirical formulas that are both transparent and computationally straightforward.

It is helpful to discuss first about the pairwise difference representation of the covariances between general random variables. Let X, Y be random variables with finite second moments; write $\mathbb{C}\{X, Y\} := \mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)(Y - \mu_Y)\}$ where means $\mu_X = \mathbb{E}\{X\}$ and $\mu_Y = \mathbb{E}\{Y\}$. If $(X_1, Y_1)'$ and $(X_2, Y_2)'$ are i.i.d. replications of the random vector $(X, Y)'$, then observing

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(Y_1 - Y_2)\} &= \mathbb{E}\{X_1 Y_1\} + \mathbb{E}\{X_2 Y_2\} - \mathbb{E}\{X_1\}\mathbb{E}\{Y_2\} - \mathbb{E}\{X_2\}\mathbb{E}\{Y_1\} \\ &= 2(\mathbb{E}\{XY\} - \mathbb{E}\{X\}\mathbb{E}\{Y\}) = 2\mathbb{C}\{X, Y\}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

it is easy to see that

$$\mathbb{C}\{X, Y\} = \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(Y_1 - Y_2)\} = \mathbb{E}\{X_1(Y_1 - Y_2)\}. \quad (2.2)$$

The second equality shows that only one of the variables in $(X, Y)'$ need be replicated to avoid centering with respect to the means (μ_X and μ_Y). The above two equations also hold under the weaker assumption (without identical distributions) that $(X_1, Y_1)'$ and $(X_2, Y_2)'$ have the same first and second moments as (X, Y) with $\mathbb{E}\{X_1 Y_2\} = \mathbb{E}\{X_2 Y_1\} = \mathbb{E}\{X\}\mathbb{E}\{Y\}$. This representation is applicable when $X_1 = Y_1$ and $X_2 = Y_2$. We then derive the following formulae for the variances of X :

$$\sigma_X^2 = \text{Var}(X) = \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\} = \mathbb{E}\{X_1(X_1 - X_2)\}. \quad (2.3)$$

The uncentered second moment of X can be written as

$$\mathbb{E}\{X^2\} = \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\} + \mu_X^2 = \mathbb{E}\{X_1(X_1 - X_2)\} + \mu_X^2. \quad (2.4)$$

We define more formally about what we mean by the D -representation of a parameter.

Definition 2.1. *A parameter γ has a D -representation for the variables X_1, \dots, X_n if there is a function $g(x_1, \dots, x_n) = h(x_2 - x_1, \dots, x_n - x_{n-1})$ such that*

$$\gamma = \mathbb{E}\{h(X_2 - X_1, \dots, X_n - X_{n-1})\}. \quad (2.5)$$

In other words, γ has a D -representation for the variables X_1, \dots, X_n if it can be written as the expected value of a function $g(X_1, \dots, X_n)$ which depends on X_1, \dots, X_n only through the differences between the variables X_1, \dots, X_n . This means that $g(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ is invariant to uniform location changes.

A potential useful feature of the representation (2.2) follows from the fact that the variables $(X_1 - X_2)$ and $(Y_1 - Y_2)$ have marginal distributions symmetric around zero. Consequently, the odd moments of $(X_1 - X_2)$ and $(Y_1 - Y_2)$ are all zero (when they exist). More generally, the distribution of the vector $(X_1 - X_2, Y_1 - Y_2)'$ is jointly symmetric around zero in the sense that

$$(X_1 - X_2, Y_1 - Y_2)' \sim -(X_1 - X_2, Y_1 - Y_2)'. \quad (2.6)$$

This type of symmetry can be useful for proving unbiasedness results in various setups; see [Dufour \(1984\)](#) and [Dufour \(1985\)](#). This property is shared by all D -representations when the paired differences are based on i.i.d. observations.

We can now show that the empirical moment discussed in (1.4) can be derived from the general moment formula (2.2). Consider observed pairs $\{(x_i, y_j)\}_{i,j=1}^n$ of the random vector (X^*, Y^*) where the values x_1, \dots, x_n and y_1, \dots, y_n need not be distinct, and let (I, J) be pair of random integers on $i, j = 1, \dots, n$ such that $\mathbb{P}[(I, J) = (i, j)] = (\frac{1}{n})^2$, we can write $\mathbb{E}\{X^*\} = \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n x_i = \bar{x}$, and similarly $\mathbb{E}\{Y^*\} = \bar{y}$. By the definition of the covariance,

$$\sigma_{X^*Y^*} = \mathbb{E}\{X^*Y^*\} - \mathbb{E}\{X^*\}\mathbb{E}\{Y^*\} = \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n x_i y_j - \bar{x}\bar{y}. \quad (2.7)$$

Alternatively, the covariances between X^* and Y^* can be represented by the expected value of the pairwise differences of two i.i.d replications of (X^*, Y^*) , (X_1^*, Y_1^*) and (X_2^*, Y_2^*) , using (2.2);

$$\sigma_{X^*Y^*} = \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}\{(X_1^* - X_2^*)(Y_1^* - Y_2^*)\} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n (x_i - x_j)(y_i - y_j). \quad (2.8)$$

Since the above sum contains a zero whenever $i = j$, it is natural to divide by $(n^2 - n)$ rather than n^2 . This leads to:

$$s_{X^*Y^*} := \frac{n}{n-1} \sigma_{X^*Y^*} = \frac{1}{2n(n-1)} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n (x_i - x_j)(y_i - y_j). \quad (2.9)$$

In the special case where $X^* = Y^*$,

$$\sigma_{X^*}^2 = \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}\{(X_1^* - X_2^*)^2\} = \frac{1}{2n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n (x_i - x_j)^2, \quad s_{X^*}^2 = \frac{1}{2n(n-1)} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n (x_i - x_j)^2 \quad (2.10)$$

where the latter is the Gini formula (1.2) for the variance.

Finally, consider the random vectors (X, Y) is fitted to the ordinary least square model. Then, the linear regression coefficient of Y on X can be expressed as

$$\beta_{Y.X} = \frac{\sigma_{XY}}{\sigma_X^2} = \frac{\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(Y_1 - Y_2)\}}{\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\}} = \frac{\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)Y_1\}}{\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)X_1\}}. \quad (2.11)$$

Its empirical counterpart follows by replacing expectations with averages over ordered index pairs (i, j) . Together, these results show that covariances, variances, and linear relations can be expressed through pairwise differences of i.i.d. replications of random variables alone.

3. Skewness and Kurtosis via Pairwise Differences

Skewness and kurtosis can be expressed without explicit centering by writing the third and fourth central moments through differences of i.i.d. replications. Let X admit finite moments as needed, and let X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4 denote i.i.d. replications of X . The first important observation is that the third and fourth central moments of a random variable X can be interpreted as covariances, which in turn can be expressed in terms of pairwise differences between replicated random variables.

Proposition 3.1 (Covariance Representation of Third and Fourth Central Moments). *Let X be a random variable with finite mean μ_X and variance σ_X^2 . Let X_1 and X_2 be two i.i.d. replications of X . If X has finite third moment, then*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^3\} &= \mathbb{C}\{X, (X - \mu_X)^2\} = \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(X_1 - \mu_X)^2\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(X_1^2 - X_2^2)\} - \mu_X \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

If X has fourth moment, then

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^4\} &= \mathbb{C}\{X, (X - \mu_X)^3\} = \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(X_1 - \mu_X)^3\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(X_1^3 - X_2^3)\} - 3\mu_X\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^3\} - 3\mu_X^2\sigma_X^2.\end{aligned}\quad (3.2)$$

More generally, we can write (3.1) as

$$\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^3\} = \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}\{[(X_1 - \mu_X) - (X_2 - \mu_X)][(X_1 - \mu_X)^2 - (X_2 - \mu_X)^2]\}, \quad (3.3)$$

so that $\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^3\}$ measure the association between a change in the deviation from the mean and the corresponding change in the absolute values of the deviations. A positive (negative) association entails positive (negative) skewness, which is clearly exhibited by pairwise differences.

It is possible to avoid dependence on unknown parameters (μ_X and σ_X^2) in Proposition.(3.1) by using a large number of i.i.d. replications of the random variable. For the third moment, consider X_1, X_2, X_3 three i.i.d. replications of X : then by (3.1),

$$\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^3\} = \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)[(X_1^2 - X_2^2) - 2X_3(X_1 - X_2)]\}. \quad (3.4)$$

For the fourth moment, consider X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4 four i.i.d. replications of X : then by (3.2),

$$\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^4\} = \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(X_1^3 - X_2^3) - 3X_3(X_1 - X_2)(X_1^2 - X_2^2) + 3X_3X_4(X_1 - X_2)^2\}. \quad (3.5)$$

The key benefit of using i.i.d. replications X_i and X_j of a random variable X ($i \neq j$) is that

$$\mu_X = \mathbb{E}\{X_i\} = \mathbb{E}\{X_j\}, \quad \mathbb{E}\{X_i X_j\} = \mathbb{E}\{X_i\}\mathbb{E}\{X_j\}. \quad (3.6)$$

In other words, the expectation of the product of the i.i.d replications is equal to the product of the expectation of the i.i.d replications. The formal D -representation are derived in the following propositions.

Proposition 3.2 (D -Representation of Third Central Moment). *Let X be a random variable with mean μ_X , variance σ_X^2 , and a finite third moment. If X_1, X_2, X_3 are three i.i.d. replications of X , then*

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^3\} &= \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_3)(X_1 - X_2)^2\} = \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)[(X_1 - X_3)^2 - (X_2 - X_3)^2]\} \\ &= \frac{9}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - \bar{X}^{(3)})(X_2 - \bar{X}^{(3)})(X_3 - \bar{X}^{(3)})\}\end{aligned}\quad (3.7)$$

where $\bar{X}^{(3)} := \sum_{j=1}^3 X_j/3$.

Proposition 3.3 (D -Representation of Fourth Central Moment). *Let X be a random variable with mean μ_X , variance σ_X^2 , and a finite fourth moment. If X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4 are four i.i.d. replications of X , then*

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^4\} &= \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^4\} - \frac{3}{4}(\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\})^2 \\ &= \mathbb{E}\{\frac{1}{2}(X_1 - X_2)^4 - \frac{3}{4}(X_1 - X_2)^2(X_3 - X_4)^2\}.\end{aligned}\quad (3.8)$$

We can now apply the above results to skewness, kurtosis, and excess kurtosis coefficients:

$$\text{Sk}(X) := \frac{\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^3\}}{\sigma_X^3}, \quad \text{Kur}(X) := \frac{\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^4\}}{\sigma_X^4}, \quad \text{EKur}(X) := \text{Kur}(X) - 3 \quad (3.9)$$

Proposition 3.4 (*D-Representation of Skewness and Kurtosis*). *Let X be a random variable with mean μ_X , variance σ_X^2 , and X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4 are four i.i.d. replications of X . If X has finite third moment, then*

$$Sk(X) = \frac{\sqrt{8}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_3)(X_1 - X_2)^2\}}{(\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\})^{3/2}}. \quad (3.10)$$

If X has finite fourth moment, then

$$Kur(X) = \frac{2\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^4\}}{(\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\})^2} - 3. \quad (3.11)$$

If X_1 and X_2 are i.i.d. normal, it is easy to see that

$$\frac{\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^4\}}{(\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\})^2} = \frac{12\sigma_X^4}{4\sigma_X^4} = 3, \quad (3.12)$$

so that $\mathbb{E}Kur(X) = 0$.

4. Recursions for High-order Moments

We show that higher-order central moments can possess expressions that depend only on pairwise differences of i.i.d. realization of a random variable, thereby avoiding explicit centering. Let X be a random variable with mean μ_X and finite moments up to order $n \geq 1$, and write the k -th central moment as

$$\mu_k := \mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^k\}, \quad k = 1, \dots, n. \quad (4.1)$$

Consider i.i.d. replications X_0, X_1, \dots, X_n of X and let $\tilde{X}_i := X_i - \mu_X$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$. Then $\tilde{X}_0, \dots, \tilde{X}_n$ are independent and

$$\mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_i\} = \mu_1 = 0, \quad \text{for } i = 0, \dots, n. \quad (4.2)$$

A baseline identity valid for any order n is obtained by the product of differences using $n + 1$ replications, let $P_k := \prod_{i=1}^k (X_0 - X_i)$, then

$$\mathbb{E}\{P_k\} = \mathbb{E}\left\{\prod_{i=1}^k (\tilde{X}_0 - \tilde{X}_i)\right\} = \mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_0^k\} = \mu_k, \quad k = 1, \dots, n. \quad (4.3)$$

From (4.3), P_k can be viewed as an unbiased estimator of μ_k for $k = 1, \dots, n$, and this immediately shows that all the central moments of X have a D -representation for moments up to order n , provided X has moments up to order n . For the low orders of practical interest, one can reduce replication and work entirely with differences (see Section 3 for $n = 2, 3, 4$). For higher orders $n \geq 5$, we can use recursions.

Proposition 4.1 (*Recursions for Higher-order Moments*). *Let X be a random variable with mean μ_X , and finite central moments μ_j for $j = 1, \dots, n + 1$, where $n \geq 1$. If X_1, X_2, X_3 are three i.i.d. replications of X , then*

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{n+1} &= \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(X_1 - \mu_X)^n\} \\ &= \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_3)(X_1 - X_2)^n\} - \sum_{j=2}^{n-1} (-1)^j C_n^j \mu_j \mu_{n+1-j}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.4)$$

where $C_n^j = n!/[j!(n-j)!]$ and, for $n + 1$ even,

$$\mu_{n+1} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^{n+1}\} - \sum_{j=2}^{n-1} (-1)^j C_{n+1}^j \mu_j \mu_{n+1-j} \right]. \quad (4.5)$$

Consider the following sequences of functions for the i.i.d. replications X_1, \dots, X_n of X with $n \geq 5$,

$$\bar{\mu}_1 = 0, \quad (4.6)$$

$$\bar{\mu}_2(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{2}(x_1 - x_2)^2, \quad (4.7)$$

$$\bar{\mu}_3(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{2}(x_1 - x_2)^2[(x_1 - x_3) + (x_2 - x_3)], \quad (4.8)$$

$$\bar{\mu}_4(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = \frac{1}{2}(x_1 - x_2)^4 - \frac{3}{4}(x_1 - x_2)^2(x_3 - x_4)^2, \quad (4.9)$$

and for $k \geq 4$,

$$\bar{\mu}_{k+1}(x_1, \dots, x_{k+1}) = (x_1 - x_3)(x_1 - x_2)^k - \sum_{j=2}^{k-1} (-1)^j C_k^j \bar{\mu}_j(x_1, \dots, x_j) \bar{\mu}_{k+1-j}(x_{j+1}, \dots, x_{k+1}). \quad (4.10)$$

If $k + 1$ is even (with $k \geq 1$), by (4.5), we can use the function

$$\tilde{\mu}_{k+1}(x_1, \dots, x_{k+1}) = \frac{1}{2} \left[(x_1 - x_2)^{k+1} - \sum_{j=2}^{k-1} (-1)^j C_{k+1}^j \bar{\mu}_j(x_1, \dots, x_j) \bar{\mu}_{k+1-j}(x_{j+1}, \dots, x_{k+1}) \right]. \quad (4.11)$$

Therefore, the functions $\bar{\mu}_k(x_1, \dots, x_k)$ and $\tilde{\mu}_k(x_1, \dots, x_k)$ depend on their arguments only through the pairwise differences $x_i - x_j$ ($i, j = 1, \dots, k$).

Proposition 4.2 (Recursive D-Representations for Higher-order Moments). *Let X be a random variable with mean μ_X , and finite moments up to order $n + 1$, where $n \geq 1$, and let $\bar{\mu}_k(x_1, \dots, x_k)$ and $\tilde{\mu}_k(x_1, \dots, x_k)$ be defined by (4.6) -(4.11) for $k \geq 1$. If X_1, \dots, X_{n+1} are i.i.d. replications of X , then*

$$\mathbb{E}\{\bar{\mu}_{k+1}(X_1, \dots, X_{k+1})\} = \mu_{k+1}, \quad \text{for } k = 1, \dots, n, \quad (4.12)$$

and, if $k + 1$ is even

$$\mathbb{E}\{\tilde{\mu}_{k+1}(X_1, \dots, X_{k+1})\} = \mu_{k+1}, \quad \text{for } k = 1, \dots, n. \quad (4.13)$$

The above proposition shows that the k -th central moment of X has a D -representation which only requires k replications of X (provided that μ_k is finite).

5. Applications

The D -representations derived earlier lead directly to unbiased estimation of central moments. The key observation is that each target central moment of a real random variable X can be written as the expectation of a kernel which only depends on pairwise differences of a small number of i.i.d. replications of X . For $k \geq 2$, the k -th central moment of X only requires k i.i.d. replications X_1, \dots, X_k , write

$$\mu_k := \mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^k\} = \mathbb{E}\{h_k(X_1, \dots, X_k)\}, \quad \text{for } k \geq 2, \quad (5.1)$$

where

$$h_2(X_1, X_2) = \frac{1}{2}(X_1 - X_2)^2, \quad (5.2)$$

$$h_3(X_1, X_2, X_3) = \frac{1}{2}(X_1 - X_2)^2[(X_1 - X_3) + (X_2 - X_3)], \quad (5.3)$$

$$h_4(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4) = \frac{1}{2}(X_1 - X_2)^4 - \frac{3}{4}(X_1 - X_2)^2(X_3 - X_4)^2, \quad (5.4)$$

$$h_{k+1}(X_1, \dots, X_{k+1}) = (X_1 - X_3)(X_1 - X_2)^k \quad (5.5)$$

$$- \sum_{j=2}^{k-1} (-1)^j C_k^j h_j(X_1, \dots, X_j) h_{k+1-j}(X_{j+1}, \dots, X_{k+1}), \quad k \geq 4. \quad (5.6)$$

In other words, $h_k(X_1, \dots, X_k)$ is an unbiased estimator of μ_k based on k observations.

If n observations X_1, \dots, X_n are available, any (fixed or randomly selected) subset of k observations from X_1, \dots, X_n yields an unbiased estimator of μ_k , and similarly for the arithmetic (or a weighted) average of such subsets. Specifically, for $k = 2, 3, 4$,

$$\hat{\mu}_2 = \binom{n}{2}^{-1} \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq n} \frac{1}{2}(x_i - x_j)^2 = \frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{i \neq j} \left[\frac{1}{2}(x_i - x_j)^2 \right], \quad (5.7)$$

$$\hat{\mu}_3 = \frac{1}{n(n-1)(n-2)} \sum_{i_1 \neq i_2 \neq i_3} [(x_{i_1} - x_{i_3})(x_{i_1} - x_{i_2})^2], \quad (5.8)$$

$$\hat{\mu}_4 = \frac{1}{n(n-1)(n-2)(n-3)} \sum_{i_1 \neq i_2 \neq i_3 \neq i_4} \left[\frac{1}{2}(x_{i_1} - x_{i_2})^4 - \frac{3}{4}(x_{i_1} - x_{i_2})^2(x_{i_3} - x_{i_4})^2 \right] \quad (5.9)$$

where (5.7) is also discussed by Lee (2019) in the U-statistics theory. More generally, for any $k \geq 4$, an unbiased estimator of the $(k+1)$ -th central moment can be expressed as

$$\hat{\mu}_{k+1} = (P_n^{k+1})^{-1} \sum_{i_1 \neq \dots \neq i_{k+1}} \left[(x_{i_1} - x_{i_3})(x_{i_1} - x_{i_2})^k - \sum_{j=2}^{k-1} (-1)^j C_k^j \hat{\mu}_j(x_{i_1}, \dots, x_{i_j}) \hat{\mu}_{k+1-j}(x_{i_{j+1}}, \dots, x_{i_{k+1}}) \right] \quad (5.10)$$

where $P_n^{k+1} := n!/(n-k-1)!$ is the number of ordered $(k+1)$ -permutations. We will call such estimators based on observation differences D -estimators, $\hat{\mu}_k(n)$.

It is easy to see that the computational cost of averaging over all subsets of k observations from X_1, \dots, X_n grows dramatically as n increases. As the result, we consider a practical unbiased estimator, observing that the arithmetic average of $h_k(X_{i_1}, \dots, X_{i_k})$ over N distinct randomly selected tuples $\{i_1, \dots, i_k\}$ of $\{1, \dots, n\}$ is an unbiased estimator of μ_k . This can be easily implemented through computer programming by generating the index tuples (i_1, \dots, i_k) randomly from a uniform distribution over the index set I . Due to its stochastic nature, we refer to this estimator as a Monte Carlo approximation of the D -estimator, $\hat{\mu}_k(n)^{MC}$.

It is of interest to compare D -estimators of μ_k with the ‘‘natural’’ estimators based on deviations from the sample mean

$$\hat{m}_k(n) = \frac{1}{(n-1)} \sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X}_n)^k, \quad \bar{X}_n = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n X_i. \quad (5.11)$$

For $k = 2$, $\hat{m}_k(n)$ is unbiased, but it is not generally unbiased for $k \geq 3$. To see how big the bias difference can be, we take $n = k$ and compare by simulation $\hat{\mu}_k(k)$ with the corresponding D -estimator with $h_k(X_1, \dots, X_k)$; see Table.1. We use Exponential distribution as an example because its central moments are nonzero at all orders, which helps us assess estimator bias without interference from sign-canceling or offsetting effects that occur when the true moment is zero. We see from these results that $\hat{m}_k(k)$ is heavily biased, while the corresponding D -estimators exhibit no bias as

predicted by the results presented above.

Table 1: **Simulation Comparison of Bias for Exponential(2) when $n=k$**

Central Moment Number of Observations	Ord. 2 2	Ord. 3 3	Ord. 4 4	Ord. 5 5	Ord. 6 6	Ord. 7 7	Ord. 8 8
<i>True Value</i>	0.25	0.25	0.56	1.38	4.00	14.48	57.94
Natural Estimator $\hat{m}_k(k)$	0.000	-0.167	-0.258	-0.768	-2.171	-8.321	-33.739
D-estimators $\hat{\mu}_k(k)$	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.003	0.094	0.131	0.053

* *Number of Simulation = 20000000*

When $n > k$, more efficient unbiased estimators can be obtained by averaging several minimal estimators. Table.2 presents simulation results comparing the bias of the “natural” estimators $\hat{m}_k(n)$ with the proposed D -estimator Monte Carlo approximation of central moments of orders $k = 2, \dots, 8$ under an Exponential(2) distribution. For each replication, we generate 30,000 Monte Carlo samples.

Table 2: **Simulation Comparison of Bias for Exponential(2) when $n > k$**

Central Moment	Ord.2	Ord.3	Ord.4	Ord.5	Ord.6	Ord.7	Ord.8
<i>True Value</i>	0.25	0.25	0.56	1.38	4.00	14.48	57.94
n=50							
Natural Estimator $\hat{m}_k(n)$	-0.004	-0.018	-0.059	-0.240	-0.921	-5.203	-27.483
D-Estimator MC $\hat{\mu}_k(n)^{MC}$	-0.004	-0.009	-0.035	-0.162	-0.592	-4.048	-22.484
n=100							
Natural Estimator $\hat{m}_k(n)$	-0.001	-0.008	-0.020	-0.084	-0.295	-2.621	-16.574
D-Estimator MC $\hat{\mu}_k(n)^{MC}$	-0.001	-0.003	-0.005	-0.035	-0.133	-1.991	-13.020

* *Number of Simulation = 1000*

The simulation results demonstrate that the proposed D -estimator Monte Carlo approximation substantially reduces bias across all orders of the central moment compared to the “natural” estimator. This improvement is particularly notable for higher-order moments where the naive estimator exhibits larger negative bias. Moreover, increasing the sample size from 50 to 100 decreases the bias for both estimators, but the D -estimator approach consistently outperforms the “natural” estimator at each sample size. These findings highlight the effectiveness of the Monte Carlo approximation in providing more accurate and unbiased estimates of central moments, especially for higher-order moments that are typically more challenging to estimate.

From (3.7), one can see that several choices of minimal estimator h_3 are possible (and similarly for higher-order moments), which may have different efficiency properties. The above results can also be used to build unbiased estimators of cumulants as well as to analyze which observations deviate from the rest of the sample. The latter application can be based on analyzing the population of subgroups of observations $(X_{i_1}, \dots, X_{i_k})$ along with the corresponding unbiased estimates $h_k(X_{i_1}, \dots, X_{i_k})$. Discussing in detail variants of D -estimators, as well as other applications, goes beyond the scope of this paper.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, following an approach (apparently) initiated by Gini (1912) for the variance, we presented a unified difference-based framework in which central moments are expressed as expectations of functions that depend only on pairwise differences of i.i.d. replications of random variables. Beginning with the variance and covariance identities in (1.2) and (1.4), we showed how to obtain location-free pairwise-differences representation (defined formally as D -representations) that extend naturally to higher orders. For the third and fourth central moments, we derived D -representations that yield immediate expressions for skewness and kurtosis. For general moments, we observed that central moments can be interpreted as covariances between a random variable and powers of the same variable (a *nonlinear* relation). These then provide *recursions* which link the D -representation of any moment to lower order ones, hence D -representations for all central moments

(as long as they are finite). Additionally, we constructed unbiased estimators of central moments and proposed a Monte Carlo approximation that preserves unbiasedness while controlling computation cost. Simulations comparing these estimators with conventional sample-moment “natural” estimators highlight substantial bias reductions, especially at higher orders. Finally, it is of interest to note that the formulas given in this paper can be interpreted as applications of the “coupling” method [see [Thorisson \(2000\)](#)], which opens the way to additional applications.

7. Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the William Dow Chair in Political Economy (McGill University), the Bank of Canada (Research Fellowship), the Toulouse School of Economics (Pierre-de-Fermat Chair of excellence), the Universidad Carlos III de Madrid (Banco Santander de Madrid Chair of excellence), the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada, the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada, and the Fonds de recherche sur la société et la culture (Québec).

Declaration of interest The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

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8. Appendix: Proofs

PROOF OF PROPOSITION 3.1. The third central moment can be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^3\} &= \mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)(X - \mu_X)^2\} = \mathbb{C}[X, (X - \mu_X)^2] \\ &= \mathbb{C}[X, (X^2 - 2\mu_X X + \mu_X^2)] = \mathbb{C}[X, (X^2 - 2\mu_X X)].\end{aligned}\quad (8.1)$$

Using (2.2) and (2.3), we can write:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{C}[X, (X - \mu_X)^2] &= \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)[(X_1 - \mu_X)^2 - (X_2 - \mu_X)^2]\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)[(X_1^2 - 2\mu_X X_1) - (X_2^2 - 2\mu_X X_2)]\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)[(X_1^2 - X_2^2) - 2\mu_X(X_1 - X_2)]\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(X_1^2 - X_2^2)\} - \mu_X \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(X_1^2 - X_2^2)\} - 2\mu_X \sigma_X^2.\end{aligned}\quad (8.2)$$

(3.1) follows on combining (8.1) and (8.2). To show (3.2), we proceed similarly. We have:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^4\} &= \mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)(X - \mu_X)^3\} = \mathbb{C}[X, (X - \mu_X)^3] \\ &= \mathbb{C}[X, (X^3 - 3X^2\mu_X + 3X\mu_X^2 - \mu_X^3)] \\ &= \mathbb{C}[X, (X^3 - 3X^2\mu_X + 3X\mu_X^2)].\end{aligned}\quad (8.3)$$

Hence, by (2.2),

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{C}[X, (X - \mu_X)^3] &= \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)[(X_1 - \mu_X)^3 - (X_2 - \mu_X)^3]\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)[(X_1^3 - 3X_1^2\mu_X + 3X_1\mu_X^2 - \mu_X^3) \\ &\quad - (X_2^3 - 3X_2^2\mu_X + 3X_2\mu_X^2 - \mu_X^3)]\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)[(X_1^3 - X_2^3) - 3\mu_X(X_1^2 - X_2^2) + 3\mu_X^2(X_1 - X_2)]\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(X_1^3 - X_2^3)\} - \frac{3}{2} \mu_X \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(X_1^2 - X_2^2)\} \\ &\quad + \frac{3}{2} \mu_X^2 \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(X_1^3 - X_2^3)\} - 3\mu_X [\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^3\} + \mu_X \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\}] \\ &\quad + \frac{3}{2} \mu_X^2 \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(X_1^3 - X_2^3)\} - 3\mu_X \mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^3\} - \frac{3}{2} \mu_X^2 \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(X_1^3 - X_2^3)\} - 3\mu_X \mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^3\} - 3\mu_X^2 \sigma_X^2.\end{aligned}\quad (8.4)$$

(3.2) follows on combining (8.3) and (8.4). □

PROOF OF PROPOSITION 3.2. Since X_1, X_2, X_3 are i.i.d. replications of X , we have

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)[(X_1 - X_3)^2 - (X_2 - X_3)^2]\} &= \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)[(X_1^2 - X_2^2) - 2X_3(X_1 - X_2)]\} \\ &= \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(X_1^2 - X_2^2)\} - 2\mathbb{E}\{X_3\}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\} \\ &= \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(X_1^2 - X_2^2)\} - 2\mu_X\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\}.\end{aligned}\quad (8.5)$$

Using (3.1),

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^3\} &= \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(X_1^2 - X_2^2)\} - \mu_X\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)[(X_1 - X_3)^2 - (X_2 - X_3)^2]\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)[(X_1^2 - X_2^2) - 2X_3(X_1 - X_2)]\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2[(X_1 + X_2) - 2X_3]\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2[(X_1 - X_3) + (X_2 - X_3)]\}.\end{aligned}\quad (8.6)$$

Now set $\tilde{X}_i = X_i - \mu_X$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$, so that $\mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_i\} = 0$ for all i . Using the mutual independence of $\tilde{X}_1, \tilde{X}_2, \tilde{X}_3$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_3)(X_1 - X_2)^2\} &= \mathbb{E}\{(\tilde{X}_1 - \tilde{X}_3)(\tilde{X}_1 - \tilde{X}_2)^2\} \\ &= \mathbb{E}\{(\tilde{X}_1 - \tilde{X}_3)(\tilde{X}_1^2 - 2\tilde{X}_1\tilde{X}_2 + \tilde{X}_2^2)\} \\ &= \mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_1^3\} = \mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^3\}.\end{aligned}\quad (8.7)$$

This establishes the first two identities of (3.7). Further,

$$D_i^{(3)} = \sum_{j=1}^3 D_{ij} = \sum_{j \neq i} (\tilde{X}_i - \tilde{X}_j) = 2\tilde{X}_i - \sum_{j \neq i} \tilde{X}_j, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \quad (8.8)$$

and since $\mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_i\tilde{X}_j\tilde{X}_k\} = 0$ unless $i = j = k$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}\{D_1^{(3)}D_2^{(3)}D_3^{(3)}\} &= \mathbb{E}\{(2\tilde{X}_1 - \tilde{X}_2 - \tilde{X}_3)(2\tilde{X}_2 - \tilde{X}_1 - \tilde{X}_3)(2\tilde{X}_3 - \tilde{X}_1 - \tilde{X}_2)\} \\ &= 2\mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_1^3\} + 2\mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_2^3\} + 2\mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_3^3\} = 6\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^3\}.\end{aligned}\quad (8.9)$$

The last identity of (3.7) follows from

$$X_i - \tilde{X}^{(3)} = \frac{1}{3}\left(3X_i - \sum_{j=1}^3 X_j\right) = \frac{1}{3}\sum_{j \neq i} (X_i - X_j) = \frac{1}{3}D_i^{(3)}. \quad (8.10)$$

□

PROOF OF PROPOSITION 3.3. Set $\tilde{X}_i = X_i - \mu_X$ for $i = 1, \dots, 4$. By the binomial expansion,

$$\begin{aligned}(X_1 - X_2)^4 &= (\tilde{X}_1 - \tilde{X}_2)^4 = \sum_{j=0}^4 (-1)^j C_4^j \tilde{X}_1^{4-j} \tilde{X}_2^j \\ &= (\tilde{X}_1^4 + \tilde{X}_2^4) - 4(\tilde{X}_1^3\tilde{X}_2 + \tilde{X}_1\tilde{X}_2^3) + 6\tilde{X}_1^2\tilde{X}_2^2.\end{aligned}\quad (8.11)$$

Taking expectations and using independence with $\mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_i\} = 0$ and $\mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_i^2\} = \sigma_X^2$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^4\} &= 2\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^4\} - 4(\mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_1^3\}\mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_2\} + \mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_1\}\mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_2^3\}) + 6\mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_1^2\}\mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_2^2\} \\
&= 2\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^4\} + 6\sigma_X^4 \\
&= 2\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^4\} + \frac{3}{2}(\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\})^2 \\
&= 2\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^4\} + \frac{3}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\}\mathbb{E}\{(X_3 - X_4)^2\} \\
&= 2\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^4\} + \frac{3}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2(X_3 - X_4)^2\}, \tag{8.12}
\end{aligned}$$

where the last step uses independence of (X_1, X_2) and (X_3, X_4) . Hence

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^4\} &= \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^4\} - 3\sigma_X^4 \\
&= \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^4\} - \frac{3}{4}(\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\})^2 \\
&= \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^4\} - \frac{3}{4}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2(X_3 - X_4)^2\}. \tag{8.13}
\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of (3.8). \square

PROOF OF PROPOSITION 3.4. If X has a finite third moment, Propositions 3.1 and 3.2 yield

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Sk}(X) &= \frac{\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^3\}}{\sigma_X^3} = \frac{(\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(X_1^2 - X_2^2)\}/2) - \mu_X \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\}}{\sigma_X^3} \\
&= \frac{\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_3)(X_1 - X_2)^2\}}{\sigma_X^3} = \frac{\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_3)(X_1 - X_2)^2\}}{(\sigma_X^2)^{3/2}} \\
&= \frac{\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_3)(X_1 - X_2)^2\}}{(\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\}/2)^{3/2}} = \frac{\sqrt{8}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_3)(X_1 - X_2)^2\}}{(\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\})^{3/2}}. \tag{8.14}
\end{aligned}$$

If X has a finite fourth moment, Propositions 3.1 and 3.3 give

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Kur}(X) &= \frac{\mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)^4\}}{\sigma_X^4} = \frac{\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^4\} - 6\sigma_X^4}{2\sigma_X^4} = \frac{\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^4\}}{2\sigma_X^4} - 3 \\
&= \frac{\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^4\}}{2(\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\}/2)^2} - 3 = \frac{2\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^4\}}{(\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^2\})^2} - 3. \tag{8.15}
\end{aligned}$$

\square

PROOF OF PROPOSITION 4.1. By definition, for $n \geq 1$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu_{n+1} &= \mathbb{E}\{(X - \mu_X)(X - \mu_X)^n\} = \mathbb{C}[X, (X - \mu_X)^n] \\
&= \mathbb{E}\{X(X - \mu_X)^n\} - \mu_X \mu_n. \tag{8.16}
\end{aligned}$$

Let X_1, X_2, X_3 be i.i.d. replications of X . Then

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu_{n+1} &= \mathbb{E}\{X_1(X_1 - \mu_X)^n\} - \mathbb{E}\{X_2\}\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - \mu_X)^n\} \\
&= \mathbb{E}\{X_1(X_1 - \mu_X)^n\} - \mathbb{E}\{X_2(X_1 - \mu_X)^n\} \\
&= \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)(X_1 - \mu_X)^n\}. \tag{8.17}
\end{aligned}$$

Setting $\tilde{X}_j := X_j - \mu_X$ for $j = 1, 2, 3$ and using the binomial theorem,

$$\begin{aligned} (X_1 - X_2)^n &= (\tilde{X}_1 - \tilde{X}_2)^n = \sum_{j=0}^n C_n^j \tilde{X}_1^{n-j} (-\tilde{X}_2)^j \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^n (-1)^j C_n^j \tilde{X}_1^{n-j} \tilde{X}_2^j = \tilde{X}_1^n + (-1)^n \tilde{X}_2^n + \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} (-1)^j C_n^j \tilde{X}_1^{n-j} \tilde{X}_2^j, \end{aligned} \quad (8.18)$$

where $C_n^j = n!/[j!(n-j)!]$. Multiplying by $(X_1 - X_3)$,

$$\begin{aligned} (X_1 - X_3)(X_1 - X_2)^n &= (\tilde{X}_1 - \tilde{X}_3)(\tilde{X}_1 - \tilde{X}_2)^n \\ &= (\tilde{X}_1 - \tilde{X}_3)[\tilde{X}_1^n + (-1)^n \tilde{X}_2^n] + (\tilde{X}_1 - \tilde{X}_3) \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} (-1)^j C_n^j \tilde{X}_1^{n-j} \tilde{X}_2^j. \end{aligned} \quad (8.19)$$

Taking expectations in (8.19) and using $\mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_3\} = 0$ and $\mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_1^k\} = \mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_2^k\} = \mu_k$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_3)(X_1 - X_2)^n\} &= \mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_1^{n+1}\} + \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} (-1)^j C_n^j \mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_1^{n+1-j}\} \mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_2^j\} \\ &= \mu_{n+1} + \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} (-1)^j C_n^j \mu_{n+1-j} \mu_j. \end{aligned} \quad (8.20)$$

Hence, noting $\mu_1 = 0$,

$$\mu_{n+1} = \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_3)(X_1 - X_2)^n\} - \sum_{j=2}^{n-1} (-1)^j C_n^j \mu_j \mu_{n+1-j}, \quad (8.21)$$

which establishes (4.4). When n is even, take expectations in (8.18):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^n\} &= \mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_1^n + (-1)^n \tilde{X}_2^n\} + \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} (-1)^j C_n^j \mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_1^{n-j}\} \mathbb{E}\{\tilde{X}_2^j\} \\ &= 2\mu_n + \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} (-1)^j C_n^j \mu_{n-j} \mu_j = 2\mu_n + \sum_{j=2}^{n-2} (-1)^j C_n^j \mu_j \mu_{n-j}, \end{aligned} \quad (8.22)$$

hence

$$\mu_n = \frac{1}{2} \left[\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^n\} - \sum_{j=2}^{n-2} (-1)^j C_n^j \mu_j \mu_{n-j} \right], \quad (8.23)$$

which yields (4.5). \square

PROOF OF PROPOSITION 4.2. To show (4.12), first note the result holds for $k = 1, 2, 3$ (by (2.3) and Propositions 3.2–3.4). We can then proceed by mathematical induction. Suppose (4.12) holds for $1 \leq k < n$,

$$\mathbb{E}\{\bar{\mu}_k(X_1, \dots, X_k)\} = \mu_k, \quad 1 \leq k < n. \quad (8.24)$$

For $k \geq 4$, replace (x_1, \dots, x_{k+1}) by (X_1, \dots, X_{k+1}) in (4.10) and take expectations:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}\{\bar{\mu}_{k+1}(X_1, \dots, X_{k+1})\} &= \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_3)(X_1 - X_2)^k\} \\
&\quad - \sum_{j=2}^{k-1} (-1)^j C_k^j \mathbb{E}\{\bar{\mu}_j(X_1, \dots, X_j) \bar{\mu}_{k+1-j}(X_{j+1}, \dots, X_{k+1})\}. \\
&= \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_3)(X_1 - X_2)^k\} \\
&\quad - \sum_{j=2}^{k-1} (-1)^j C_k^j \mathbb{E}\{\bar{\mu}_j(X_1, \dots, X_j)\} \mathbb{E}\{\bar{\mu}_{k+1-j}(X_{j+1}, \dots, X_{k+1})\} \\
&= \mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_3)(X_1 - X_2)^k\} - \sum_{j=2}^{k-1} (-1)^j C_k^j \mu_j \mu_{k+1-j}
\end{aligned} \tag{8.25}$$

where the last identity follows from the independence of (X_1, \dots, X_j) and $(X_{j+1}, \dots, X_{k+1})$. By (4.4), this equals μ_{k+1} , establishing (4.12). If $k + 1$ is even, then from (4.11) and (4.5),

$$\begin{aligned}
&\mathbb{E}\{\bar{\mu}_{k+1}(X_1, \dots, X_{k+1})\} \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \left[\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^{k+1}\} - \sum_{j=2}^{k-1} (-1)^j C_{k+1}^j \mathbb{E}\{\bar{\mu}_j(X_1, \dots, X_j) \bar{\mu}_{k+1-j}(X_{j+1}, \dots, X_{k+1})\} \right] \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \left[\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^{k+1}\} - \sum_{j=2}^{k-1} (-1)^j C_{k+1}^j \mathbb{E}\{\bar{\mu}_j(X_1, \dots, X_j)\} \mathbb{E}\{\bar{\mu}_{k+1-j}(X_{j+1}, \dots, X_{k+1})\} \right] \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \left[\mathbb{E}\{(X_1 - X_2)^{k+1}\} - \sum_{j=2}^{k-1} (-1)^j C_{k+1}^j \mu_j \mu_{k+1-j} \right] = \mu_{k+1}.
\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of (4.13). □